

Combined estimation of gait phase and stair slope utilizing time history data

F. Weigand^{1*}, J. Zeiss¹, M. Grimmer² and U. Konigorski¹

¹ Department of Control Engineering and Mechatronics, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany

² Locomotion Laboratory, Institute of Sport Science, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: fweigand@iat.tu-darmstadt.de

Abstract: Improving the quality of life for people with amputations through active prostheses requires appropriate knowledge of the locomotion task and gait phase of the user. A shank mounted Inertial Measurement Unit based estimation method for stair slope is presented in conjunction with an improved gait phase estimation. In contrast to prior work only one Artificial Neural Network is used for the estimation of stair slope and gait phase for all three locomotion tasks and transitions between them. Utilizing past measurements should give more information to an estimation method without the need of additional sensors. By implementing a time window of 60 samples of prior measurements the gait phase and slope estimation could be improved by around 37 % and 38 % respectively comparing mean squared errors of the complete test dataset.

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I. Introduction

The possible gain in quality of life through improved active lower limb prostheses is linked to the knowledge of needed support during locomotion.

Previously, kinematic data of the shank was used with Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to estimate the gait phase for level walking and stair ambulation [1, 2]. In this work the ANN is extended to also estimate the stair slope. This information can be used for a more detailed control during locomotion on stairs.

To improve the estimation the use of time history information of the measured variables is investigated. A time window of data can be used to improve locomotion classification and intent recognition at a specific point of time during a stride [3]. Our work extends this approach to continuous gait phase and stair slope estimation.

In contrast to our prior work [1] no separate ANNs are used for each locomotion mode of interest, resulting in a larger training dataset and no locomotion mode classification is needed ahead of gait phase estimation.

Hence, we develop one estimator for all three investigated locomotion modes level walking, stair ascent and stair descent. Finally, we will test the estimation quality during transitions between these locomotion modes.

II. Methods

In comparison to other work, gait phase estimation is treated as a continuous problem as is the stair slope estimation. Therefore, no separation of phases within a stride is required.

II.I. Experimental dataset

The same dataset as in prior work is used [1]. Twelve subjects without mobility impairments (age: 25.4

±4.5 years, height: 180.1±4.6 cm and mass: 74.6±7.9 kg) walked on an instrumented track including a staircase and a level area before and after the staircase. Each subject was equipped with an inertial measurement unit (IMU) at each shank.

II.II. Artificial Neural Network

The ANN has four fully-connected layers with a cascading structure starting with 64 neurons at the first layer and halving the number of neurons with each successive layer. The outputs are x - y -coordinates of the unit circle (-1 to 1) resulting in a polar angle representing a transformed gait phase (0 % to 100 %) as presented in [1] and a normalized representation of the stair slope in degree.

II.III. Input values

As input features for the ANN three measured variables and three calculated variables are used. The shank angular velocity $\dot{\phi}$, the translational acceleration \ddot{y} and \ddot{z} are measured by a shank mounted IMU. As a substitute for the shank angle and the translational velocities, a so-called pseudo-integration is used. The pseudo-integration is acquired by an integration followed by a first-order high-pass filter, resulting in a first-order low-pass filter. A cut-off frequency of 3 Hz and 1 Hz is selected for translational and rotational measurements respectively.

II.IV. Time history information

To further improve the estimation quality without the need of additional sensors the use of past measurements seems reasonable and can easily be implemented within an existing ANN setup.

The time history information is added by using a time window with a length of T_{window} for which all measurements of the six input values are collected. For the sample frequency of $f = 200$ Hz this results in $n =$

Figure 1: Gait phase and stair slope estimation for the artificial test trial with untrained transitions and $n = 1$.

$T_{\text{window}}f$ measurements. With a hyperparameter search using NNI (Microsoft), the optimal hyperparameters of the ANN were identified including the parameter $n_{\text{opt}} = 60$, resulting in $T_{\text{window}} = 300$ ms.

Another method to implicitly embed time history information are Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [4]. Preliminary trials showed a much higher computational cost for training RNNs without benefits in estimation quality, compared to the input feature approach proposed in this work.

III. Results and discussion

Based on the results of a cross-validation in [2] an optimized set of training, validation and test subjects is selected. All following results show test data from subject ten.

By comparing the results of the ANN without to the ANN with time history information ($n_{\text{opt}} = 60$) the hypothesized benefit of a time window can be evaluated.

As a quantitative measure the mean absolute error (MAE) is used. Evaluating the whole test dataset the estimation without time history information results in MAEs of 2.99 % for the back transformed gait phase and 4.21° for the stair slope. In comparison, the time window $n_{\text{opt}} = 60$ yields MAEs of 1.89 % and 2.60° respectively. Thus, in general gait phase and stair slope estimation can benefit from a time window approach by around 37 % and 38 % respectively.

For evaluating estimation quality during transitions, sequences of strides from the test data including transitions are combined to generate an artificial test trial unavailable in the experimental setup.

It has to be noted that all transitions between locomotion modes, as marked in Figure 1 and 2, are not part of any training or validation data and hence represent a new unlearned mode of locomotion with respect to the ANN.

Comparing $n = 1$ and $n_{\text{opt}} = 60$ for the artificial test trial, the MAEs are 2.92% against 2.08 % for the back transformed gait phase and 3.71° against 3.91° for the stair slope.

The differences in the MAEs for the gait phase estimation can also be seen in Figure 1 and 2. With the use of a time window the gait phase estimation becomes smoother and large errors (> 20 %) disappear especially during transition periods. The slope estimation with a time window results in

Figure 2: Gait phase and stair slope estimation for the artificial test trial with untrained transitions and $n_{\text{opt}} = 60$.

an slightly higher MAE, but seems to have smoother estimation during level walking.

Besides the discussion of the benefits of a time window the results also show a good generalization capability of the ANN for gait phase and slope estimation during unlearned transition periods. Transitions between locomotion modes are part of everyday life activities and a good gait phase estimation for these transition strides gives the opportunity to support the user properly.

IV. Conclusion

Based on prior work, we improved the capability of the gait phase estimation by reducing the MAE and eliminating the need for separate ANNs for each locomotion mode.

Furthermore, we enabled the additional estimation of the stair slope. Besides the possible use for selecting appropriate support for different stair slopes, the slope information can be used for a basic classification between level walking, stair ascent, and stair descent.

The use of time history information of the shank further improves the gait phase estimation. However, long time windows come with the cost of larger networks and memory-intensive training datasets. A reduction to the most relevant input features based on a sensitivity analysis could be beneficial.

With the shown results for untrained transition periods in between locomotion modes a safe use of the presented approach on an active ankle prosthesis seems likely and will be approached in future work.

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